

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF CHILD EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation. The preschool system is the foundation of human life. Education, development of the child and his indicators of school readiness are the main task of today's preschool education system, which is aimed at the individual in the process of preschool education and education of the child. The article will talk about the personality of the child, the attention paid to his upbringing.

Keywords: child life, preschool education system, modern approach, upbringing, types of upbringing, responsibility.

The preschool system serves as a cornerstone for human maturation. Today, the development of this system in our country is rising to the level of policy. In ensuring the implementation of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021" dated December 29, 2016 PQ-2707, it is necessary to radically improve the level of training of children for school education, apply modern educational programs to the educational process, provide qualified pedagogical personnel, create conditions, it was intended to consistently continue the work of strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions. A plan of measures for the implementation of the tasks set out in the program for 2017-2021 on further improvement of the preschool education system was developed.

At the present stage of development of the educational system, rapid changes are taking place in preschool education, which is considered its first link, and they are manifested in the following: the current and normative basis of the activities of preschool educational institutions is improving; preschool educational institutions are moving to new types of financial and economic activities; the network of non-state preschool educational institutions is expanding; ; alternative forms of preschool educational institutions are being introduced on the basis of short-term groups.

Preschool education is an educational and educational process that ensures the physical and psychic development of the child, taking into account the individual and age characteristics of the child, makes it the basis for the further stage of continuing education - schooling, is purposefully oriented in all aspects. Preschool education should perform the following tasks, regardless of its forms and methods:

- strengthening the physical and psychic health of children;
- to attract children to national, universal, ancient and cultural values;
- development of the mental, intellectual potential of the child;
- formation of high moral and spiritual qualities on the basis of national traditions and achievements;
- systematically and purposefully prepare children for education in school, develop their individual characteristics and talents.

The above testifies that the preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan should ensure the comprehensive development of the child according to the requirements of the state and society, taking into account the individual characteristics. The feature of preschool age is that it is during this period that general development is ensured, as a result of which the foundation is laid for the acquisition of various manifestations of any social knowledge, skills, skills and activities in the future.

Based on the fact that the educational process is aimed at the personality of the child, the education of preschool children should be carried out on the basis of the principles of collaborative pedagogy, consisting of a system of methods and methods of Education, based on creative and humanitarian principles in the development of the individual. The main cases of pedagogical cooperation are the attitude to education as the mutual creative cooperation of the educator and the child; teaching without coercion; the idea of a difficult goal (a complex goal is set before the child and a sense of confidence is instilled in him that he will overcome it); use of the base (base signals); self-analysis (discussion of the results of children's activities individually and in a team); Free Choice (Choice by the Educator of teaching time, voluntarily setting children's better assimilation of the curriculum as a goal); intellectual background of the group (setting significant life goals at this stage of training and acquiring wider knowledge

The results of education are manifested in the transformation of personal qualities in a child, such as nowfulness, kindness, sociability, truthfulness, truthfulness, striving for Purpose, initiative, boldness, Organization, hard work,

feeling responsible, elegance, restraint, Valor, independence, workmanship, observability, resourcefulness.

In the process of preschool education, the model of education that is directed to the individual when educating the child is considered a priority. The purpose of a conscious approach to the individual is to develop the individual, not to “change” him under the given standard and pressure, but to “accept him as he is”. The personal approach seeks to create conditions for the development and full manifestation of personal obligations of participants in the educational process. Personal obligations are the manifestation of certain qualities that apply the social order of “being a person” by a person.

Determining the direction of the educator among the values determines his professional activity. The approach to personality allows the educator and the child to feel as a person, to identify and manifest their capabilities, to realize themselves, to self-awareness, self-confidence and self-discovery methods that can be carried out by society.

In preschool age, the child acquires high peaks in the adoption of special superficial features of objects, finds a solution to practical and mental tasks of a visual form. But the child will still be irrelevant to the appearance of the items. This is natural, because objects exist for him, and they interest the child only as an object of practical and mental activity. A preschool child acts not on the essence of the items, but on their appearance and use. There is a big difference between how things look to us and the essence. The essence of the items is not superficial, it does not arise behind personal experience, it is not accepted directly. It is discovered through a socially organized study – a scientific understanding of the world.

As a conclusion, we can say that the above indicates that in the implementation of a personality-oriented approach, the development of a holistic subject of the educational process should be carried out, and not a separate development of the personality of the child and educator. This system manifests itself as indicators of the development of a holistic subject.

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КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМАХ (pp. 30-32).

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